

SOLUTION OF THE THIRD INITIAL-BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM FOR A HYPERBOLIC TYPE EQUATION USING THE FOURIER METHOD

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Let the equation

$$u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx} \quad (1)$$

be given in halfway $0 < x < l, t > 0$ with the following boundary conditions

$$u_x(0, t) = 0, u_x(l, t) - hu(l, t) = 0, h > 0 \quad (2)$$

and initial conditions

$$u|_{t=0} = \varphi(x), u_t|_t = \psi(x) \quad (3)$$

to solve the given equation, we use the method of separating the solution from variables. First, the non-trivial solution of equation (1) satisfying conditions (2) is sought in the form

$$u(x, t) = X(x) \cdot T(t) \quad (4)$$

using Fourier's method of separation of variables. Substituting (4) into equation (1), we obtain the equation

$$X(x) \cdot T''(t) = a^2 X''(x) T(t)$$

When we divide this equation by $X(x) \cdot T(t)$, we obtain a simple differential equation of the form

$$T''(t) + a^2 \lambda^2 T(t) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$X''(x) + \lambda^2 X(x) = 0 \quad (6)$$

with respect to the functions $T(t)$ and $X(x)$, where λ is an unknown constant parameter. Also, the solutions of equations $X(x)$ and $T(t)$ have the form

$$X(x) = A \cos \lambda x + B \sin \lambda x$$

$$T(t) = C \cos a \lambda t + D \sin a \lambda t.$$

Substituting (4) into (2), considering that $T(t) \neq 0$, it follows that the function $X(x)$ must satisfy the conditions

$$X'(0) = 0, \quad X'(l) - hX(l) = 0,$$

From it, solution $X(x) = \cos \lambda x$ is obtained. where $\text{ctg} \mu_k = \frac{\mu_k}{lh}$ and $\mu_k = \lambda_k l$,

it6 means that we have the eigenfunction

$$X_k(x) = \cos \lambda_k x$$

Where, $\mu_k = \lambda_k l$, $k=1,2,3,\dots$, then

$$T_k(t) = C_k \cos a\lambda_k t + D_k \sin a\lambda_k t.$$

Now it follows from the found $X_k(x)$ and $T_k(t)$ according to (4) that

$$u_k(x,t) = X_k(x) \cdot T_k(t) = (C_k \cos a\lambda_k t + D_k \sin a\lambda_k t) \cos \lambda_k x \quad (7)$$

Since function (1) is a non-trivial solution of equation (2) satisfying condition (2), then the infinite sum of solutions (7) is also a solution, that is

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (C_k \cos a\lambda_k t + D_k \sin a\lambda_k t) \cos \lambda_k x \quad (8)$$

We differentiate (8) with respect to t :

$$u_t(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a\lambda_k (-C_k \sin a\lambda_k t + D_k \cos a\lambda_k t) \cos \lambda_k x \quad (9)$$

Assuming $t=0$ in (8) and (9), based on the initial conditions (3), we obtain the following equalities

$$u(x,0) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} C_k \cos \lambda_k x = \varphi(x), \quad u_t(x,0) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a\lambda_k D_k \cos \lambda_k x = \psi(x)$$

Now let's find the unknowns C_k , D_k from these equations, then

$$C_k = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l \varphi(x) X_k(x) dx, \quad D_k = \frac{2}{\lambda_k a} \int_0^l \psi(x) X_k(x) dx, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Substituting these into (4), we obtain the solution of the third mixed problem (1), (2), (3).

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